

Surface engineering of activated carbon with dopamine functionalization for sustainable screen-printed supercapacitor

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Development of fully eco-friendly screen-printed sustainable supercapacitor.
- Dopamine eliminates the need of Texilac drying retarder in screen printing.
- Device achieves specific capacitance of 23 F g^{-1} at current density of 0.5 A g^{-1} .
- Device deliver specific energy of 7.2 W h kg^{-1} at a specific power of 1.6 kW kg^{-1} .

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Quinone-functionalized pristine activated carbon (PAC) electrode offers enhanced ion storage capabilities for SC electrodes, yet producing biocompatible, cost-effective materials with precisely controlled surface groups remains a substantial challenge. In this study, dopamine-functionalized activated carbon (DFAC) composites were synthesized using a π - π stacking approach. Notably, the DFAC electrode ink was screen-printed without the use of a drying retardant, while the PAC ink required the Texilac drying retarder to facilitate screen printing. Amine and catechol group present in dopamine enhance surface energy, improve wettability and dispersion, and promote adhesion through hydrogen bonds, ensuring smoother, more durable, and consistent printing. Redox peaks at potentials of 0.45 V and 0.5 V with respect to an Ag/AgCl reference electrode are observed, associated with the hydroquinone-quinone couple, confirming the presence of dopamine. DFAC based SCs (28 F g^{-1}) also demonstrates significantly higher specific capacitance than PAC-based SCs (10.8 F g^{-1}). At 0.5 A g^{-1} current density, the screen-printed SCs deliver a specific capacitance of 23 F g^{-1} . A specific energy of 7.2 W h kg^{-1} and a specific

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power of 1.6 kW kg^{-1} were obtained at 1.5 A g^{-1} current density. DFAC paves the way for biodegradable SCs, creating new opportunities for powering low-energy wireless sensors.

1. Introduction

The European Commission's Energy Roadmap 2050 identifies energy storage as a crucial technology for achieving a low-carbon economy. Additionally, the growing demand for electric vehicles and portable electronics, along with the advancement of the Internet of Things, necessitates the need for affordable and sustainable energy solutions [1]. Batteries have become a fundamental part of our everyday lives. However, there are specific areas where they fall short or fail to meet requirements, including: (i) low power density, (ii) the redox reactions that occur within batteries can cause Joule heating and thermochemical heating during use. If this heat is not adequately managed, it can lead to overheating, thermal runaway, and even fire and (iii) limited cycle life and (iv) typically environmentally benign materials when compared with battery materials. Although supercapacitors (SC) have roughly one-tenth the energy density of batteries, they can provide up to one hundred times greater power density and support charge-discharge cycles at high rates that are a thousand times more frequent and safer than those of batteries [2].

SCs often referred to as electrochemical capacitors, are characterized by their superior power output, high reversibility, extended lifespan, straightforward operation, and ease of integration with electronic systems [3,4]. SCs are broadly classified into two primary categories based on their energy storage mechanisms: pseudocapacitors and electrical double-layer capacitors (EDLCs). Pseudocapacitors rely on faradaic reactions, involving rapid and reversible redox processes of electroactive species. In contrast, EDLCs store energy by accumulating electrostatic charges at the interface between the electrode and the electrolyte. Consequently, materials with high surface areas that allow easy access to electrolyte ions play a critical role in their performance [5,6]. Metal oxides, conductive polymers, carbon-metal oxides and composites made of carbon and conducting polymers exhibit pseudocapacitance due to faradaic redox reactions [7]. These materials contribute to enhancing the energy density of SCs. The growing focus on sustainable energy storage technologies has significantly accelerated progress in developing eco-friendly electrode, electrolyte and current collector materials for SCs. Composites synthesized by combining carbon with metal oxides and conducting polymers are still regarded as environmentally harmful. As a result, synthesizing composites of pristine activated carbon (PAC) and bio-derived quinone materials is seen as a more favorable option compared to using carbon with metal oxides and conductive polymers. Quinone-based compounds, including synthesize melanin, tannins, and lignin are known for their redox activity, which enhances charge storage in SCs through pseudocapacitance [8–11]. Quinones and their derivatives have been extensively utilized to enhance the electrochemical properties of carbon electrodes. In this context, researchers have successfully synthesized bio-sourced quinone-based composites as promising materials for advanced energy storage applications. For instance, drop casting of sepia melanin (452 F g^{-1} at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1}) and catechin/tannic acid (300 F g^{-1} at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1}) on treated carbon paper [8], carbon cloth functionalized using polydopamine (61 F g^{-1} at current density of 1 A g^{-1}) [12], hydroquinone on activated charcoal (200 F g^{-1} at scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} for single electrode) [13], emodin modified graphene (58.9 F g^{-1} at scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1}) [14] etc. However, the electrode fabrication methods primarily reported in literature are mainly drop casting, and to the authors knowledge, there are no existing reports on dopamine-functionalized pristine activated carbon (PAC). Industrial SCs are still made of PAC derived from coconut shells as electrode material [15]. This makes it convincing to investigate the electrochemical performance of composites synthesized through π - π stacking or doping of the biodegradable molecule dopamine onto PAC

for SC applications.

Moreover, printed electronics marks a significant transformation in SC fabrication by introducing a variety of straightforward, cost-effective, and efficient manufacturing methods. These processes are adaptable, eco-friendly, and enable the creation of innovative SC designs, such as micro, asymmetric, and flexible structures [6]. This approach paves the way for maximizing the capabilities of SCs in next-generation electronic devices. Recently, numerous studies have explored various methods for fabricating SCs, such as photolithography, plasma etching, electrodeposition, and additive manufacturing. However, these techniques often involve complex and costly processes, which present significant challenges for their commercial viability. Screen printing, as a modern coating technique, enables ink to be transferred through a stencil using a squeegee, creating precise patterns on the underlying substrate. The deposition accuracy can be finely controlled by adjusting the mesh size of the screen and the viscosity of the ink. Due to its versatility in accommodating various types of ink, screen printing has gained attention as a promising approach to overcoming the challenges mentioned in recent studies [16]. Its compatibility with a wide range of substrates, including flexible materials like paper and plastics, has enabled significant advancements across various electronic applications, including sensors, displays, RFID tags, and energy storage devices like SCs [17]. We have previously demonstrated the fabrication of monolithic SCs via screen printing, using PAC as the electrode material combined with Texilac drying retardant (EPTAINKS TEXILAC RITARDANTE M167380L001000) to make it screen-printable [16,18]. The objective of this current study is to eliminate Texilac (which compromised the electrochemical performance of the device) from the ink formulation and introduce bio-sourced pseudocapacitive materials to enhance the electrochemical performance of the SCs. Bio-sourced quinone-based compounds, including melanin, tannins, and lignin are known for their redox activity, which enhances charge storage in SCs through pseudocapacitance [8]. PAC serves as effective conductive scaffolds during the redox reactions of small organic molecules, enhancing the electrochemical properties of these compounds. Dopamine integrates redox-active functional groups, including catechol and amine groups, into the electrode material. These groups undergo rapid and reversible redox reactions, enhancing pseudocapacitance and improving charge storage capacity. Additionally, the presence of hydrophilic catechol molecules increases wettability in aqueous solutions, facilitating more efficient charge transfer at the electrode/electrolyte interface [19]. This improved wettability and redox activity contributes to enhanced ion diffusion kinetics, promoting efficient ion transport and overall electrochemical performance. Most researchers tend to use carbon cloth and graphene as the carbon substrate, which can be costly and complex to produce, and electrode fabrication methods primarily reported in the literature are mainly drop casting.

This study investigates the electrochemical performance of dopamine-functionalized activated carbon (DFAC) electrode materials. Screen printing techniques are employed to fabricate the current collector and electrode materials. The electrochemical performance of DFAC is compared to that of PAC electrodes using both three-electrode and two-electrode systems in aqueous electrolyte. Furthermore, the research aims to develop a screen-printed, environmentally friendly SC using a combination of cellulose di-acetate (CDA) as substrate, graphite ink as current collector, DFAC as electrode, deep eutectic solvent electrolyte, and cellulose as separator. Here, we have utilized environmentally friendly deep eutectic solvent-based electrolyte composed of choline chloride and urea. Finally, we have comprehensively examined the electrochemical performance of SCs fabricated with screen-printed DFAC electrodes and the deep eutectic solvent electrolyte.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

The Optimont® CDA film (cellulose di-acetate, 115 μm thick) was obtained from Bleher Folientechnik GmbH, Germany. Kuraray Chemical Co., Japan, provided the pristine activated carbon powder (YP-80F). N, N-Dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.5 %), sodium chloride, Dopamine hydrochloride, urea, chitosan (derived from shrimp shells, product code 50494) and choline chloride were procured from Sigma-Aldrich. All reagents were utilized without further purification. Deionized Milli-Q grade water (Millipore, Merck) was employed throughout the experiments.

2.2. Synthesis of dopamine functionalized activated carbon (DFAC) particles

The synthesis of dopamine-functionalized activated carbon (DFAC) was carried out according to the procedure detailed in our previous work, utilizing the solvothermal method [9]. Initially, a specific amount (1 g, 2 g and 3 g) of dopamine hydrochloride was dissolved in 40 mL of DMF at room temperature using a magnetic stirrer. Subsequently, 10 g of PAC was introduced into the solution, followed by a 30 min sonication to achieve a homogeneous dispersion. This dark, homogeneous mixture was then transferred to a 120 mL autoclave and heated at 180 °C for 12 h (optimized parameter in terms of the yield of DFAC). The product was meticulously rinsed with deionized water until it reached a neutral pH, ensuring all unbound DFAC was removed. It was then dried in a hot air oven at 90 °C for 12 h.

2.3. Synthesis of deep eutectic solvent-based (DES) electrolyte

To prepare the DES electrolyte, urea and choline chloride were mixed in a 1:2 M ratio [20]. The mixture was continuously stirred at 80 °C, until a clear, uniform liquid was obtained. Once cooled to room temperature, the liquid was stored in a borosilicate glass reagent bottle.

2.4. Fabrication of screen-printed symmetric supercapacitors

A chitosan-based binder solution was used as the basis for screen-printing inks. The binder was prepared by combining 1.7 g of chitosan, 67.6 g of water, and 0.7 g of acetic acid, which were stirred overnight [18]. Inks for printing the electrodes were formulated by adding 3.09 g of powdered active material and 2.0 g of water to 6.89 g of the prepared binder solution. Additionally, 4 g of Texilac drying retardant was added to the PAC ink. The inks were mixed in a polyethylene bag and carefully homogenized with a roller to achieve a consistent texture. The viscosity versus shear rate for all inks was measured at room temperature using a rotational rheometer (TA Instruments Inc., USA). The results displayed in Fig. S1. Symmetric SCs for aqueous electrolytes were fabricated on commercial aluminium-laminated polyethylene terephthalate (PET) film from Pyroll (Al/PET thickness 9 μm /50 μm , respectively). Current collectors and electrodes were screen-printed on the PET side of the film, while aluminium served as a barrier layer against electrolyte evaporation on the outside of the SCs. Printing was carried out using a sheet-to-sheet Ekra X5 professional stencil printer (Scanditron Sverige AB, Sweden), and the printing parameters presented in Table 1.

Rectangular current collectors, with lateral dimensions of 34 mm \times 31 mm were first printed using a commercial graphite ink (LOCTITE EDAG PF 407C E&C), after which they were dried in a 95 °C oven for 1 h. Electrodes (PAC and DFAC) with dimensions of 33 mm \times 10 mm were printed on the cured graphite layer, and cured for 30 min at 60 °C, resulting in an average electrode mass of 8.1 mg and 6.3 mg, with PAC and DFAC, respectively. Dry thicknesses of $27 \pm 1 \mu\text{m}$ and $22 \pm 1 \mu\text{m}$ were obtained for the printed current collectors and electrodes,

Table 1

Screen printing parameters of current collector and electrode.

	Current collector	Electrode
Mesh parameters		
Mesh count (1/cm)	24	48
Thread diameter (μm)	125	55
Printing parameters		
Printing speed (mm/s)	20	20
Squeegee force (N)	200	200
Snap-off (mm)	2.00	1.50

respectively (Fig. S2). Electrolyte was applied to the cured electrodes with a micropipette, and a piece of cellulose paper (Dynacap GT 0.45/40, Glatfelter Gernsbach GmbH) was placed as an ion-permeable separator between the electrodes. Half of the samples were loaded with an aqueous NaCl electrolyte (NaCl: H₂O mass ratio 1:5), and the other half with the DES electrolyte. Due to its viscous nature, the DES was let to soak on the electrodes overnight to fully immerse the porous structure of the electrodes. Finally, the SCs were assembled by aligning the electrodes and sealing the devices with an adhesive tape (3M 468 MP). Fig. 1 shows the digital photo of screen printed SCs.

2.5. Electrochemical characterization

2.5.1. Three electrode measurements

To examine the faradaic effects of dopamine, the electrochemical properties of PAC and DFAC electrodes were first assessed using a three-electrode configuration. These measurements were performed with a Zahner electrochemical workstation (ZAHNER-elektrok GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). PAC and DFAC electrodes (measuring 22 mm \times 10 mm, with electrode material masses of approximately 3 mg cm⁻² for PAC and 2 mg cm⁻² for DFAC) functioned as the working electrodes. For the three-electrode measurements, a 125 μm PET Melinex ST506 film was chosen as the substrate (Fig. S1). A coil-shaped platinum wire and a silver/silver chloride electrode were used as the counter and reference electrodes, respectively. The experiments were conducted in a 50 mL standard electrochemical cell (redoxme AB, Sweden).

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was performed at different scan rates (2, 5, 8, 10, and 20 mV s⁻¹) in an aqueous NaCl electrolyte, with a NaCl to deionized water mass ratio of 1:5, within a potential range of 0–1.0 V vs. Ag/AgCl. The specific capacitance for PAC and DFAC electrodes was determined from the fifth cycle of the CV curves using Eq. (1) [8].

$$C_{cv} = \frac{\int I \cdot dV}{\nu m \Delta V} \quad (1)$$

Here, $\int I \cdot dV$ signifies the integrated area under the curve, ν is the scan rate (mV s⁻¹) m is the mass of the electrode (g), and ΔV is the used potential range (V).

2.5.2. Two electrode measurements

Galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) and CV analyses of SCs in a two-electrode configuration were performed using a Maccor 4300 instrument (Maccor, Inc., USA). The total mass loading of active materials for the SCs was approximately $3 \pm 0.5 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$ for PAC and $2.2 \pm 0.5 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$ for DFAC across both electrodes. The CV scans were executed over a potential range of 0–1.2 V at scan rates of 5, 10, 50, and 100 mV s⁻¹. Simultaneously, GCD measurements were carried out at current densities of 0.15, 0.5, and 1.5 A g⁻¹. The GCD data were analyzed to determine equivalent series resistance (ESR) and specific capacitance values using Eq.s (2) and (3) [21]. Specific energy (W h kg⁻¹) and specific power (W kg⁻¹) for DFAC-based SCs were calculated from the GCD data using Eq.s (4) and (5) [10].

$$C_{device} = \frac{I \Delta t}{m \Delta V} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Diagrammatic representation of the SC manufacturing process.

$$ESR = \frac{V_{\text{drop}}}{\Delta I} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Specific Energy } (S_E) = \frac{C_{\text{device}} \times \Delta V^2}{2 \times 3600} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Specific Power } (S_P) = \frac{S_E}{\Delta t} \quad (5)$$

Where, C_{device} represents the specific capacitance of the SC (F g^{-1}), I is the current applied (A), m is the mass of both electrodes (g), Δt is the discharge duration (s) and ΔV is the voltage drop observed during Δt .

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electrochemical performance of DFAC and PAC screen printed electrode in three electrode systems

In our prior publications, we have comprehensively examined the material characterization techniques for DFAC electrode material. These techniques include the determination of specific surface area and pore size distribution using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller method, the identification of dopamine peaks at higher wavelength shifts (2927 and 3073 cm^{-1}), Raman spectroscopy, distinct mass loss via thermogravimetric analysis, and the identification of amines ($-\text{NH}_2$) by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy electrode material [9]. In this paper, we focus primarily on the electrochemical characterization of the SCs fabricated by screen printing. In this study, we optimized the dopamine dosage by considering two key parameters: the yield of the solvothermal reaction and the weight ratio of dopamine to PAC (0.1, 0.2, and 0.3). For all ratios, the final product yield exceeded 90%. However, in terms of electrochemical performance, a dopamine-to-PAC weight ratio of 0.2 exhibited slightly better charge storage capacity, as shown in Fig. S3. Based on these findings, we conducted all subsequent electrochemical studies using this optimized ratio. To evaluate the redox properties of DFAC, we investigated the electrochemical behavior of both PAC and DFAC electrodes

within a three-electrode configuration. As illustrated in Fig. 2a, the CV curve for DFAC, measured at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} within a potential range of $0-1.0 \text{ V}$, displays voltammetric currents nearly double those of PAC. Additionally, distinct redox peaks are observed around 0.5 and 0.4 V vs. Ag/AgCl , corresponding to the hydroquinone-quinone redox pair, confirming the dopamine functionalization [8]. When CV curves were recorded at scan rates ranging from ($2-20 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$), the PAC electrode demonstrated EDLC behavior, while the DFAC electrode exhibited a mix of pseudocapacitive and EDLC behavior (Fig. 2b and c).

This suggests a robust electronic interaction between dopamine and PAC. From the CV measurements, the specific capacitance was determined to be 43 F g^{-1} for the PAC-based electrode and 107 F g^{-1} for the DFAC-based electrode at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} . This clearly shows that dopamine functionalization greatly improves the electrochemical performance of the PAC electrode. The charge storage kinetics in PAC and DFAC were examined using Trasatti's method [22]. This method separates the total charge stored in an electrode into three parts: the faradaic charge from the slow insertion of H^+ ions, limited by ion diffusion within the solid phase; the faradaic charge from rapid surface charge-transfer reactions, known as pseudocapacitance; and the non-faradaic charge from the rapid formation of the electric double layer. The first process is identified as diffusive charge storage, while the latter two are considered capacitive charge storage. Trasatti's analysis uses specific equations to describe these charge storage mechanisms. The total charge stored (Q_t) in the electrode material consists of two distinct components, as shown in Eq. (6).

$$Q_t = Q_c + Q_d \quad (6)$$

Where, Q_c denotes the capacitive charge storage, encompassing both electric double layer and pseudocapacitive contributions, whereas (Q_d) refers to the diffusive charge storage. Based on Eq. (6), the main charge storage mechanism can be identified using Eqs (7) and (8)

$$Q_v = Q_c + \alpha v^{-0.5} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2. (a) CV curves at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} , (b) CV curves at different scan rates for PAC, (c) CV curves at different scan rates for DFAC, (d) Normalized Q_v versus $v^{-0.5}$, (e) Plot of the reciprocal normalized Q_v versus $v^{0.5}$ for PAC and DFAC electrodes (solid and dotted lines denote the linear fits for PAC and DFAC data points, respectively. Inset illustrates the root mean square and the linear fit equation), and (f) Ratio of charge storage contributions (capacitive and diffusive) for PAC and DFAC electrodes.

$$\frac{1}{Q_v} = \frac{1}{Q_t} + \alpha v^{0.5} \quad (8)$$

Here, Q_v represents the total voltammetric charge measured, where Q_c denotes the capacitive charge from both the electric double layer and pseudocapacitive effects, and Q_t is the total stored charge. The variable v signifies the scan rate, and α is constant. According to Eq. (7), as v approaches infinity, the diffusive charge storage is minimized, allowing the intercept of the Q_v vs. $v^{-0.5}$ plot (Fig. 2d) to represent the capacitive charge storage Q_c . In Eq. (8), when v nears zero, the reaction time is sufficiently long for ions to access all electrode sites, enabling the extrapolation of the $1/Q_v$ vs. $v^{-0.5}$ plot (Fig. 2e) to determine the total stored charge Q_t at the intercept. The diffusive charge storage Q_d can then be calculated as the difference between Q_t and Q_c . The diffusive charge storage in PAC and DFAC accounts for 28.6 % and 59.2 % of the total charge, respectively (Fig. 2f). The findings reveal that pseudocapacitance, mainly originating from dopamine, accounts for approximately 30 % of the total capacitance. This trend is consistent across scan rates from 1 to 10 mV s^{-1} , with variations attributed to differences in PAC. The greater diffusive charge storage in DFAC suggests more extensive intercalation/de-intercalation, resulting in higher charge storage capacity (specific capacitance). This is likely due to the presence of dopamine molecules in PAC, which facilitate easier ion diffusion within the structure. The charge storage mechanisms of PAC and DFAC electrodes have been thoroughly analyzed [9]. The two electroactive materials, PAC and dopamine, operate through different mechanisms. PAC primarily relies on an electrostatic process, while dopamine functions mainly through pseudocapacitance. During the initial charging, dopamine undergoes oxidation at the positive electrode, resulting in an increase in oxidized species (dopamine quinones). H^+ and sodium cations move into the aqueous electrolyte, while anions are incorporated into the electrode material. Dopamine quinones are reduced at the negative electrode, releasing chloride anions into the electrolyte and allowing cations to be absorbed by the electrode. These reactions are

reversed during discharge. Additionally, charge storage is maintained by electrolyte ions at the interface between the electrode and the electrolyte, balancing the electrode charge. The combination of pseudocapacitive and electrostatic mechanisms is essential for charge storage in DFAC SCs.

3.2. Electrochemical performance of PAC and DFAC screen printed SCs in aqueous electrolyte

Screen-printed symmetric SCs based on DFAC and PAC electrode materials were fabricated. Comparison curves of CV and GCD of PAC and DFAC SCs under the same test conditions are presented in Fig. 3a and b. The obtained results showed that the larger CV integral area and longer charge/discharge time for DFAC SCs indicate superior electrochemical properties compared to PAC SCs. Specifically, DFAC SCs exhibit a specific capacitance of 28 F g^{-1} at 0.5 A g^{-1} , far exceeding that of PAC SCs (10.8 F g^{-1}). A plausible explanation is that dopamine functionalization significantly decreased the specific surface area (from 2243 to $1901 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and pore volume (from 1.35 to $1.12 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$) of PAC [9], which likely inhibited water evaporation, thereby making the material printable without the use of Texilac drying retardant. Additionally, dopamine contains hydroxyl groups (-OH) and amine groups (-NH₂). Amine groups on PAC increase surface energy, improving wettability and uniform dispersion in the printing medium. These groups enhance adhesion by forming hydrogen bonds, leading to better print quality and durability. They also prevent agglomeration, ensuring stable, homogeneous dispersion crucial for consistent printability. Amine groups can react with components in the medium, promoting chemical compatibility for smoother printing [23,24]. Hydroxyl groups further enhance adhesion, improving substrate bonding. This enhancement provides excellent electron transport capacity and ion migration capacity. These results indicate the successful fabrication of the DFAC composite and highlight the effect of dopamine on improving charge

Fig. 3. Comparison of (a) CV curves recorded at 5 mV s^{-1} , (b) GCD curves recorded at 0.5 A g^{-1} for PAC and DFAC SCs, (c) Nyquist plots for PAC and DFAC SCs are presented with the insets showing the modified Randles circuit used for fitting, and the impedance spectra at high frequencies (the solid lines are the fitting results) (d) cycling performance of PAC and DFAC SCs over 10,000 charge-discharge cycles at current density of 1.5 A g^{-1} .

storage performance. The specific capacitances of DFAC SCs have been calculated to be 31, 28, and 25 F g^{-1} at current densities of 0.15, 0.5, and 1.5 A g^{-1} , respectively. Notably, these values are significantly higher than those of PAC SCs across various current densities. As the current density increases, the capacitance of DFAC SCs decreases gradually. Moreover, even at a current density of 1.5 A g^{-1} , the DFAC SCs maintain a specific capacitance of 25 F g^{-1} , indicating their excellent rate performance. The charge storage kinetics of PAC and DFAC SCs are further investigated by EIS. EIS analysis for PAC and DFAC-based SCs was conducted, and the resulting Nyquist plots are shown in Fig. 3c.

EIS measurements were conducted with an applied amplitude of 5 mV at open circuit potential, within a frequency range from 10 mHz to 10 MHz. The real component of the complex impedance at 1 kHz from the Nyquist plot was analyzed to determine the ESR value [2]. The values were determined to be 13.4Ω for the DFAC-based SCs and 14.4Ω for the PAC-based SCs. The fitted parameters for the modified Randles circuit of both devices are summarized in Table 2. The mass transfer and diffusion characteristics of the electrode material are directly reflected by the slope of the line observed in the low-frequency region, which corresponds to Warburg diffusion impedance. Notably, the DFAC SCs exhibit a steeper line, demonstrating their enhanced ability for mass and ion transport. In addition, cycling performance is a key factor in assessing electrode lifetime. It is noteworthy that SCs based on PAC and DFAC can maintain up to 96 % and 92 % of their original capacitance,

Table 2
Equivalent circuit parameters of PAC and DFAC based SCs.

Device	Element						
	L_0 (nH)	R_0 (Ω)	W_0 (mDW)	R_1 (Ω)	CPE ₀		C_0 (mF)
					Y_0 (mSs ^{α})	α (m)	
PAC	175	13.5	760	1	5.45	262	107
DFAC	150	12.3	731	1.3	1.12	536	205

respectively, after 10,000 cycles, showcasing outstanding electrochemical stability and reversibility (Fig. 3d). For the first 7000 cycles, the capacitance retention decreases for DFAC devices, followed by an increase in capacitance beyond this point. A similar trend was reported by Purkait et al., 2020 in their study on dopamine-functionalized reduced graphene oxide (rGO) composites [25]. As shown in their work, the capacitance retention initially decreases over the first 7000 cycles, then increases up to 40,000 cycles, before gradually declining to 53,000 cycles.

This improvement in capacitance over multiple cycles may be attributed to the presence of hydrophilic functional groups (e.g., catechol and amine groups) in DFAC devices, which enhance aqueous electrolyte wettability [19]. This, in turn, facilitates ion diffusion and charge storage efficiency, contributing to the observed increase in capacitance. The DFAC SCs demonstrated a specific energy of 5 Wh kg^{-1} and a specific power of 1.6 kW kg^{-1} at a current density of 1.5 A g^{-1} . The findings suggest that dopamine functionalization not only enhances the printability but also facilitates electron flow and conduction, thereby boosting the charge storage capacity.

3.3. Electrochemical performance of DFAC screen printed SCs in DES electrolyte

To evaluate the practical performance of the DFAC electrode materials, biobased SCs were fabricated for testing. SCs are fabricated using environmentally friendly components, such as the cellulose di-acetate substrate, graphite ink current collector, DFAC ink electrode material, DES electrolyte, and cellulose paper separator. As a result, the DFAC-based SCs supports sustainability and environmentally friendly practices. Fig. 4a shows the GCD profiles of DFAC and PAC based SCs at the same current density (0.5 A g^{-1}) within the voltage window of 0–1.8 V. The findings provide clear evidence of the electrochemical performance of DFAC-based SCs, exhibiting the same behavior with both DES-based and aqueous electrolytes. The CV and GCD profiles of DFAC-based SCs

Fig. 4. (a) Comparison of GCD curves of PAC and DFAC based SCs recorded at current density of 0.5 A g^{-1} , (b) CV curves at different scan rates, (c) GCD curve at various current densities for DFAC SCs, (d) Cycling stability test of PAC and DFAC based SCs recorded at current density of 0.5 A g^{-1} , (e) Nyquist plots (insets shows the high frequency region and equivalent circuit used for fitting) and (f) Bode diagram for DFAC based SCs recorded before and after 10,000 cycles.

at different scan rates and current densities are illustrated in Fig. 4b and c. The CV curves exhibit an ideal quasi-rectangular shape, with the current response values increasing sharply as scan rates rise. Even at a high scan rate of 100 mV s^{-1} , there is no significant distortion of the CV curves, indicating efficient charge storage with capacitive characteristics.

The GCD curves also show quasi-linear symmetric triangles, reflecting capacitive behavior, and confirm that the coulombic efficiency (CE) of the SCs is close to 100 %. The specific capacitances of DFAC SCs are 29, 23, and 16 F g^{-1} at current densities of 0.15, 0.5, and 1.5 A g^{-1} , respectively. After 10,000 cycles, the DFAC SCs retain 67 % of their initial capacitance, with the CE remaining near 100 % throughout the charge/discharge process, showcasing their structural durability and stability (Fig. 4d). EIS was employed to analyze the ion diffusion dynamics, reaction kinetics, and evaluate the ESR of the DFAC SCs depicted in Fig. 4e. Fitting parameters obtained from the proposed equivalent circuit are displayed in Table 3.

As seen in Fig. 4e, the Nyquist plots obtained prior to and following the life cycle test confirm the device's ability to maintain stable electrochemical performance, demonstrating its robustness and cyclic stability over prolonged use. A semicircle is observed in the high-frequency region, while a quasi-straight line appears in the low-frequency region. The small diameter of the semicircle before cycling indicates minimal resistance, implying a more efficient ions/electrons transport path. After

cycling, the EIS spectra show an increase in charge transfer resistance, suggesting an extended ions transport pathway. Additionally, the reduction in the slope observed in the low-frequency domain of the Nyquist plot indicates a rise in diffusion resistance, indicating a more sluggish ion diffusion process at the interface. The Nyquist plots also reveal that the ESR of the SCs rose from 11Ω to 13.4Ω after the cyclic test, which is consistent with the GCD test results, where the ESR increased from 19.6Ω to 23Ω . For NaCl electrolyte, both devices are showing more than 90 % capacitance retention rate over 10,000 charge-discharged cycles. However, DFAC devices with DES electrolytes show poor cycling rate around (67 % post 10000 cycles). Post cycling, in the low-frequency domain of the Nyquist plot indicates a rise in interfacial diffusion resistance, indicating slower ion diffusion process at the interface which resulted in the lower capacitance. A possible reason could be degradation of electrode material over 10,000 cycles. Table 3 presents the Nyquist plot fitting results before and after cycling, showing a higher Warburg diffusion element (DW) post-cycling, confirming slower ion diffusion. Mouloudi et al., 2021 fabricated a symmetric PDA-FCC device, consisting of a polydopamine nanofilm on oxygen-functionalized carbon cloth electrodes, with a PVA- H_2SO_4 electrolyte [12]. Their study demonstrated a 74 % retention rate after 10,000 cycles. This decline in performance is primarily attributed to the over-oxidation or over-reduction of the electrode active materials, which serve as a potential degradation pathway during prolonged GCD cycling. The quinone/hydroquinone redox activity introduced by dopamine contributes beneficial pseudocapacitance initially but may also undergo irreversible side reactions or structural rearrangements over prolonged operation. In addition, the inherently high viscosity and lower ionic conductivity of the DES electrolyte can hinder efficient ion transport and increase interfacial resistance, further contributing to performance decay over time. Future improvements could focus on optimizing the interaction between DES electrolytes and the binder used in electrode fabrication. While this study primarily focused on optimizing the ink recipe and printing parameters using cellulose-based

Table 3

Equivalent circuit parameters for DFAC based SCs before and after cycling.

Device (DFAC based SC)	Element						
	L0 (nH)	R0 (Ω)	W0 (DW)	R1 (Ω)	CPE0		C0 (mF)
					Y0 (μSs^{α})	α (m)	
Pre cycling	186	9.74	2.42	1.58	842	617	127
Post cycling	115	11.2	32	2	1	1000	115

binder, which were specifically chosen for their eco-friendly and water-soluble properties, we have not explored other binder materials in this work. However, future studies could investigate the use of more robust and electrochemically stable binders. For instance, incorporating binders that are more stable under redox cycling, such as carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) or other advanced binder formulations, could help maintain electrode integrity and stabilize dopamine redox chemistry during prolonged cycling. Such improvements could enhance long-term performance and facilitate more efficient ion transport, which would be crucial for advancing the cycling stability of DES-based systems.

It is worth noting that ESR derived from EIS are typically lower than those obtained from GCD analysis [2]. Bode plots (Fig. 4f) further show a post-cycling an increase in ESR, changes in phase angles, decline in capacitance, and shifts in frequency response. From the GCD analysis, the SCs exhibited an ESR of 20 Ω . It is also important to highlight that SCs without metallic current collectors typically have a noticeably higher ESR, a trend that has been consistently observed in prior studies. In cases where a 25 μm layer of graphite ink is applied, the sheet resistance was measured at around 20 $\Omega \text{ sq}^{-1}$, which aligns with the manufacturer's specifications [26]. Therefore, it can be deduced that the main factor contributing to the ESR observed in the SCs is the relatively high ohmic resistance of the printed graphite layers. It is crucial to perform comparative assessments of the electrochemical properties of synthesized electrode materials, regardless of their similarities or differences. Achieving this requires ensuring consistency in both the fabrication and testing conditions. Key factors such as coating thickness or mass loading of electrode, material of construction of the current collector, applied current for GCD testing, composition of electrolyte (regarding ionic conductivity) many other relevant parameters play a crucial role in assessing the electrochemical performance of developed electrode materials [2,3,5]. As far as we are aware, no prior studies have employed the same combination; therefore, a comparison of the developed SC in this work with reported studies is not valid. However, we have selected only those research papers that have used either printing methods for fabrication or quinone-carbon-based electrode materials in symmetrical supercapacitors and the comparison of electrochemical properties are summarized in Table 4. The DFAC SCs achieved a specific

energy of around 7.2 W h kg^{-1} and a specific power of 1.6 kW kg^{-1} at a current density of 1.5 A g^{-1} . The Ragone plot in Fig. 5a depicts the relationship between specific energy and power at different current densities. It also compares the performance of the present work with other recent high-performance devices. The obtained specific energy and power values align with those reported in the literature for composites synthesized via printing methods using activated carbon or carbon and bio-derived quinone in symmetric SCs [16,18,20,21,27–30]. Additionally, bending tests on the devices were also investigated. The results, as shown in Fig. S4, demonstrate that the DFAC-based device retains excellent flexibility and maintains stable performance under bending conditions.

To evaluate the practical applicability of our supercapacitor as a power source, we used it to illuminate a commercially available green LED with forward voltage of approximately 1.8 V. The device (two cells connected in series) was charged from 0 to 3.6 V at a current density of 0.5 A g^{-1} using a Maccor 4300 electrochemical workstation. It was then discharged through the LED, which emitted bright light for 10 min, as shown in Fig. 5b to g. This result highlights the efficient energy storage and discharge performance.

We fully acknowledge that the specific capacitance and energy density of our symmetric SCs do not exceed the highest values reported in the cited studies, particularly when compared to materials such as MXenes, transition metal oxides, carbon nanotubes, and graphene. However, the primary aim of our work is not solely to maximize these performance parameters, but rather to demonstrate the feasibility of using eco-friendly, earth-abundant, and sustainable materials in SC fabrication. While our electrochemical performance may surpass state-of-the-art benchmarks for fully biodegradable and printed supercapacitor systems, we believe our approach contributes meaningfully to the global shift towards greener and more sustainable energy storage devices. Our SCs is designed to power low-power wireless systems, where long-term stability, green fabrication, and material sustainability are often more critical than achieving maximum capacitance. This aligns with our goal to integrate biodegradable materials and eco-friendly methods into the fabrication of electronic devices, advancing the development of sustainable technology solutions. The devices we are

Table 4

Comparison of the electrochemical performance of symmetrical supercapacitors fabricated using printing methods or quinone-carbon-based electrode materials.

Device (electrode fabrication method)	Specific Capacitance	Voltage window	Specific energy	Specific power	Retention rate	Ref.
DFAC NaCl DFAC (screen printed)	31 F g^{-1} at 0.15 A g^{-1} 25 F g^{-1} at 1.5 A g^{-1} 52.9 F g^{-1} at 5 mV s^{-1} 66 mF cm^{-2} at 0.33 mA cm^{-2}	1.2 V	5 W h kg^{-1} at 1.5 A g^{-1}	1600 W Kg^{-1} at 1.5 A g^{-1}	92 % post 10,000 at 1.5 A g^{-1}	This work
DFAC DES DFAC (screen printed)	29 F g^{-1} at 0.15 A g^{-1} 16 F g^{-1} at 1.5 A g^{-1}	1.8 V	7.2 W h kg^{-1} at 1.5 A g^{-1}	1600 W Kg^{-1} at 1.5 A g^{-1}	67 % post 10,000 at 1.5 A g^{-1}	This work
DAC NaCl DAC (3D printed)	20 F g^{-1} at 0.8 A g^{-1}	1.2 V	4 W h kg^{-1}	58 W h kg^{-1}	81 % post 10,000 at 0.8 A g^{-1}	[27]
AC NaCl AC (screen printed)	9.1 F g^{-1} at 0.06 A g^{-1}	1.2 V	1.92 W h kg^{-1}	0.51 W h kg^{-1}	95 % post 10,000 at 0.06 A g^{-1}	[18]
AC NaCl AC (screen printed)	15.6 F g^{-1} at 0.2 A g^{-1}	1.2 V	3.11 W h kg^{-1}	2.5 kW kg^{-1}	99 % post 2000 at 2 A g^{-1}	[16]
3DG DES 3DG (slurry-coating and calendaring)	100 F g^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1}	2.2 V	7 W h kg^{-1}	1000 W kg^{-1}	90 % post 25,000 at 1 A g^{-1}	[20]
Graphite/activated carbon/CNF/CNC CNC/glycerol/NaCl graphite/activated carbon/CNF/CNC (3D printed)	25.6 F g^{-1} at 1 mV s^{-1}	1.2 V	0.88 W h kg^{-1}	830 W h kg^{-1}	99 % post 2000 at 0.4 A g^{-1}	[21]
C-PDA-1-3 1 M H_2SO_4 C-PDA-1-3 (Drop casting)	218 F g^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1}	1.0 V	7.59 W h kg^{-1}	500 W kg^{-1}	–	[28]
Emodin/PPy@CF PVA- H_2SO_4 Emodin/PPy@CF (Galvanostatic polymerization)	46.53 F g^{-1} at 5 mV s^{-1}	1.0 V	1.05 mW h cm^{-3}	18.92 mW cm^{-3}	86.23 % post 2000	[31]
AC NaCl AC (screen printed)	16 F g^{-1} at 0.125 A g^{-1}	1.2	–	–	–	[32]
AC PVA- H_3PO_4 AC (Gravure-offset and blade coating)	45 mF cm^{-2} at 0.3 mA cm^{-2}	0.8 V	–	–	86 % post 1200	[33]

AC: activated carbon (YP-80F), 3DG: three-dimensional graphene hydrogel electrode, CNF:cellulose-nanofibrils, CNC:cellulose-nanocrystals, C-PDA-1-3: activated carbon (0.2) to polydopamine (0.6) ratio, PPy@CF:Polypyrrole on flexible carbon fiber substrate.

Fig. 5. (a) Ragone plot comparing the DFAC device with similar carbon-based symmetric SC devices from previous studies and (b–g) Practical demonstration of the DFAC device, where two SCs connected in series illuminate a light-emitting diode.

working on are versatile and have applications in portable electronics, environmental monitoring sensors, and healthcare devices. The adaptable and multifunctional nature of biodegradable materials offers groundbreaking potential to reduce the environmental footprint of electronic devices, helping minimize harmful waste.

4. Conclusions

DFAC electrode ink was screen-printed without a drying retardant, while the PAC ink required Texilac Ritardante to extend curing time. Remarkably, the DFAC electrode exhibits nearly double the voltammetric currents compared to the PAC electrode. The PAC electrode demonstrates typical EDLC behavior, while the DFAC electrode shows a hybrid performance, combining both EDLC and pseudocapacitive characteristics in the three-electrode configuration. The presence of redox-active moieties, such as catechol and amine groups, not only contributed to additional faradaic charge storage but also improved the surface interaction with the electrolyte. Enhanced hydrophilicity, resulting from the polar functional groups, promoted better electrolyte infiltration and facilitated ion transport across the electrode–electrolyte interface. These combined effects led to improved pseudocapacitive performance and more efficient ion diffusion, underscoring the potential of dopamine-functionalized materials for high-performance supercapacitor applications. The fully bio-based screen-printed SCs developed in this work exhibit a specific capacitance of 23 F g^{-1} at 0.5 A g^{-1} . Additionally, the SC demonstrated a maximum specific energy of 7.2 Wh kg^{-1} at a specific power of 1.6 kW kg^{-1} . These results demonstrate considerable potential for DFAC as an eco-friendly electrode material for SCs especially in low-power internet of things (IoT) devices.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Chirag Mevada: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Aapo Kattainen:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Vijay Singh Parihar:** Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Jari Keskinen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Matti Mäntysalo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.237596>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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